

Kinetics and Mechanism of Electron Transfer Reactions of Aquo-thallium(III) with Hexitols in Acid Perchlorate Medium

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The kinetics of electron transfer reactions of aquo-thallium(III) with D-mannitol, D-glucitol and D-galactitol have been investigated under the pseudo-first order conditions. The variation of rate constant with hexitol concentration suggests the formation of an intermediate complex prior to the rate-determining step of its disproportionation. The rate decreases with increase in acidity, and is strongly inhibited by complexing chloride and acetate ions. Equilibrium constants of the complex formation between thallium(III) and acetic acid, chloro acetic acid and propionic acid have been computed from the observed retardation in rate of the electron transfer reaction of thallium(III) with D-mannitol by these complexing monocarboxylic acids. Corresponding aldohexoses have been confirmed as initial reaction products. Free radical formation has been confirmed by the induced polymerisation reaction with acrylonitrile and also by the epr spin trapping technique. Rate law has been derived from the proposed mechanistic steps to explain the kinetic and other results of this study.

Alditols are acyclic polyhydric alcohols that are derived from the monosaccharide sugars by reduction. Their wide-spread occurrence in nature particularly in the lower forms of life, points to their biological importance. Thallium(III) is a fairly moderate two-equivalent reagent and has been used in the kinetic studies with aldo and keto hexoses¹. In the present communication the results of the kinetic studies of the title reactions are reported.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry was studied in the presence of an excess concentration of hexitol to avoid further oxidation of more reactive products. The corresponding aldohexoses were confirmed as initial reaction products by paper chromatography and other usual qualitative procedures. Thus, the results that one mole of each hexitol (D-mannitol, D-glucitol and D-galactitol) have consumed one equivalent of thallium(III), can be explained by the stoichiometric equation (1),

when thallium(III) was present in large excess (~20–25 fold), the hexitol molecule was further oxidised to lower monosaccharides—formaldehyde and formic acid were confirmed as intermediate products by spot test with chromotropic acid and also by the paper chromatography.

Formation of free radicals during these reactions was confirmed by the polymerisation reaction induced with acrylonitrile in the dark and also by the technique of spin-trapping using epr spectroscopy². Sodium-2-sulphanatobenzylidene(*t*-butyl)-amine-*N*-oxide (SPBN), a water soluble spin trapping agent³ formed a spin adduct with the free radicals produced (Eqn. 2) which gave a very weak epr spectrum consisting of triplet of doublet. However, the spectrum became prominent and recognisable when it was recorded after the photolysis ($\lambda \geq 300$ nm) of reaction mixture containing spin-trapping agent (SPBN). The splitting constants ($a_N \simeq 0.35$ mT) : $a_H \simeq 0.35$ mT) of the resulting epr spectra suggest the formation of carbon-centred free radicals⁴ in these reactions although the proof for the thermal reactions is not very conclusive.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF k_{obs} WITH HEXITOL CONCENTRATION

$[Ti^{III}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[Hexitol] mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 k_{obs} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$					$10^5 k_o \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)} = k_{obs}/[\text{Hexitol}]$				
	D-Mannitol			D-Glucitol	D-Galactitol	D-Mannitol			D-Glucitol	D-Galactitol
	55°	65°	75°	65°	65°	55°	65°	75°	65°	65°
0.3	2.25	3.40	6.03	5.13	5.53	7.50	11.33	20.10	17.10	18.43
0.6	3.60	6.24	11.06	9.10	9.92	6.00	10.40	18.43	15.17	16.43
0.9	5.25	8.50	15.25	11.88	13.23	5.83	9.44	16.94	13.20	14.70
1.2	5.40	10.59	19.50	15.78	17.07	4.80	8.82	16.25	13.15	14.22
1.5	5.60	12.25	22.98	18.80	20.84	3.73	8.17	15.32	12.57	13.89
1.8	5.90	13.74	26.98	22.08	24.32	3.28	7.63	14.93	12.27	13.50
2.1	6.35	15.50	—	24.56	28.02	3.02	7.38	—	11.70	13.34
2.4	6.80	16.80	—	26.50	30.23	2.83	7.00	—	11.07	12.60
2.7	7.25	18.10	—	30.04	32.28	2.68	6.74	—	11.12	11.99

Kinetics of these electron transfer reactions were studied in presence of excess concentrations of hexitol and perchloric acid. The disappearance of thallium(III) with time uniformly followed first order kinetics. The pseudo-first order rate constants of the typical kinetic runs were calculated by usual procedure and also by reaction rate (R/R) method⁵. The regression analysis of the kinetic data was carried out by assuming either log of titre value or time or both subjected to error⁶. The near constant values of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) and the results of regression analysis justify the first order kinetics followed by these reactions in the present experimental conditions. The values of k_{obs} showed an increasing trend with the increase in the initial concentrations of Ti^{III} (0.6×10^{-2} to $3.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) which can be due to the dependence of the concentration of reactive species on the initial concentrations of Ti^{III} .

The second order rate constants ($k_o = k_{obs}/[\text{Hexitol}]$) decreased with increase in hexitol concentrations (Table 1) indicating the fractional order with respect to hexitol and the possibility of the complex formation. This is further supported by the non-unity slopes of $\log k_{obs}$ and $\log [\text{Hexitol}]$ linear plots.

The rate constant k_{obs} was found to decrease with increase in acidity, varied either by means of perchloric (Table 2) or sulphuric or hydrochloric acid. At a constant perchlorate ion concentration maintained by adding an appropriate quantity of sodium perchlorate solution, k_{obs} decreased inversely with hydrogen ion concentration, varied by means of perchloric acid (Table 3). Similar trend was also observed in other two acids.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF k_{obs} WITH PERCHLORIC ACID CONCENTRATION

$[Ti^{III}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Hexitol}] = 0.6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[HClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 k_{obs} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$				
	D-Mannitol			D-Glucitol	D-Galactitol
	55°	65°	75°	65°	65°
0.20	3.60	6.04	11.06	9.10	9.92
0.35	2.30	4.20	7.80	6.23	6.50
0.50	1.78	3.06	5.85	4.44	4.75
0.65	1.43	2.45	4.40	3.55	3.80
0.80	1.25	2.10	3.70	3.00	3.25
1.10	0.85	1.60	2.80	2.35	2.53
1.40	0.74	1.30	2.16	1.90	2.00

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF k_{obs} WITH HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION AT CONSTANT PERCHLORATE ION CONCENTRATION (2.0 mol dm⁻³)

 $[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-2}$ mol cm⁻³, [Hexitol] = 0.6 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 65°

[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)		
	D-Mannitol	D-Glucitol	D-Galactitol
0.2	9.46	12.88	13.80
0.5	3.98	5.32	5.80
0.8	2.61	3.52	3.70
1.1	1.85	2.61	2.75
1.4	1.60	2.10	2.25
1.7	1.35	1.70	1.80
2.0	1.10	1.47	1.52

In aqueous perchloric acid, Tl^{III} has been described as Tl³⁺ and its hydrolysed forms as Tl(OH)²⁺, Tl(OH)₂⁺ and Tl(OH)₃. In the present reactions, Tl(OH)²⁺ can be presumed to be the main reactive species of Tl³⁺, to explain the inverse dependence of rate (k_{obs}) on acidity (Tables 2 and 3).

Because of the very small value of subsequent hydrolysis constants of Tl³⁺, the formation of other hydrolysed species can be neglected. The rates of these reactions were strongly inhibited by the presence of chloride and acetate ions (Table 4). This is because these ions form complexes with Tl³⁺, thus lowering the concentration of reactive species Tl(OH)²⁺. Furthermore, the coordination sites of Tl³⁺ are blocked by these ions, and the formation of an intermediate complex is inhibited⁷.

 TABLE 4—VARIATION OF k_{obs} WITH CHLORIDE AND ACETATE IONS CONCENTRATIONS

 $[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³, [Hexitol] = 0.6 mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 0.2 mol dm⁻³, [I] = (a) 0.72 M, (b) 0.87 M, Temp = 65°

[Chloride]/ [Acetate] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
	D-Mannitol		D-Glucitol		D-Galactitol	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
0.0	6.75	7.02	9.70	9.92	10.50	10.38
0.15	4.50	4.70	6.50	6.61	6.90	6.89
0.30	2.65	2.41	2.90	3.05	3.68	3.72
0.45	1.48	1.62	2.38	2.56	2.51	2.63
0.60	—	1.23	—	1.65	—	1.85

(a) Chloride ion, (b) acetate ion variations.

It was observed that in presence of complexing monocarboxylic acids, acetic, chloroacetic and propionic acids, the rate (k_{obs}) increased proportionately with D-mannitol concentration (Table 5). The values of second order rate constant (k_0) at different acidities and temperatures are compiled in Table 6.

 TABLE 5—VARIATION OF k_{obs} WITH D-MANNITOL CONCENTRATION IN PRESENCE OF COMPLEXING CARBOXYLIC ACIDS

 $[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, [Carboxylic acid] = 0.15 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 65°

[D-Mannitol] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)			10 ⁵ $k_0 = k_{\text{obs}} / [\text{D-Mannitol}]$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹		
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)
0.3	1.06	1.58	0.38	3.53	5.27	1.27
0.6	2.16	3.17	0.75	3.60	5.28	1.25
0.9	3.26	4.77	1.20	3.62	5.30	1.33
1.2	4.35	6.33	1.61	3.62	5.27	1.34
1.5	5.32	7.80	2.01	3.55	5.20	1.34

(a) Acetic acid, (b) chloroacetic acid, (c) propionic acid.

 TABLE 6—VARIATION OF k_0 WITH COMPLEXING CARBOXYLIC ACIDS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND ACIDITIES

 $[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³, [D-Mannitol] = 0.6 mol dm⁻³, [ClO₄⁻] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³.

[HL] mol dm ⁻³	k_0 (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)					
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)
	1.0M 65°	0.75M 65°	0.50M 65°	0.25M 65°	0.25M 70°	0.25M 75°
Acetic acid						
0	3.42	4.58	6.92	13.38	18.10	24.13
0.05	3.00	3.82	5.33	8.65	11.00	12.22
0.10	2.65	3.32	4.35	6.40	7.77	8.23
0.15	2.28	2.90	3.60	5.18	6.07	6.17
0.20	2.11	2.52	3.22	4.05	4.95	5.02
0.25	1.98	2.28	2.77	3.50	4.10	4.21
Chloroacetic acid						
0	3.42	4.58	6.92	13.38	18.10	24.13
0.05	3.32	4.30	6.30	11.17	14.60	18.62
0.10	3.08	4.03	5.70	9.58	11.92	15.50
0.15	2.93	3.73	5.28	8.27	10.63	12.73
0.20	2.82	3.62	4.97	7.33	9.23	10.93
0.25	2.70	3.42	4.63	6.67	8.33	9.60
Propionic acid						
0	3.42	4.58	6.92	13.38	18.10	24.13
0.05	1.93	2.30	2.80	3.37	3.67	4.00
0.10	1.35	1.53	1.83	1.93	2.00	2.27
0.15	1.05	1.12	1.25	1.33	1.35	1.55
0.20	0.83	0.93	1.01	1.03	1.09	1.20
0.25	—	—	0.83	0.85	0.88	0.97

These kinetic results in presence of complexing carboxylic acids can be explained on the basis of the following reaction steps,

here Ti^{3+} includes both the forms of Ti^{3+} (equation 3), HL is the complexing monocarboxylic acids ($\text{L} = \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-/\text{CH}_2\text{ClCOO}^-/\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-$) and R^\bullet the free radical ($^*\text{CHOH}(\text{CHOH})_4\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$).

The rate law can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{dt} &= \frac{k[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6]}{1 + K_c[\text{HL}][\text{H}^+]^{-1}} \\ &= k_0[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}][\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Thus, it follows

$$k/k_0 = 1 + K_c[\text{HL}][\text{H}^+]^{-1} = 1 - K_E[\text{HL}] \quad (8)$$

Linear plots with unity intercept were obtained between k/k_0 vs [HL] and the values of K_E were calculated by regression analysis. The values of equilibrium constants (K_E) were then calculated

from the slopes of the linear plots of K_E and $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$. The values of the stability constants of the complexes between thallium(III) and these carboxylic acids were also computed and all these are presented in Table 7.

The activation parameters (ΔE , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger) have also been calculated for the reactions studied in absence of these complexing acids. A linear iso-kinetic plot ($\beta = 300 \text{ K}$) can be obtained in accordance with the Laffler compensation law⁸, and thus a common mechanism can be considered for all the hexitols.

The active species of Ti^{III} as expressed in equation (3) can be presumed to react with a hexitol molecule, to form an intermediate complex which disproportionates in a slow step producing free radical (R^\bullet) which then reacts with Ti^{II} to produce the respective aldohexose in a fast step.

From the data in Table 1, linear plots were obtained between $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ and $1/[\text{hexitol}]$. The values of equilibrium complex for all the hexitol complexes with thallium (III) were computed (from the linear plots) as 0.34, 0.29 and 0.25 mol^{-1} at 338 K respectively, and 1.01 and 0.28 mol^{-1} at 328 and 348 K for D-mannitol complex.

TABLE 7—VALUES OF EQUILIBRIUM AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1 COMPLEXES OF THALLIUM(III)-CARBOXYLIC ACIDS

[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	Temp. °C	K _E			K _c = K _E [H ⁺]			10 ⁻⁵ K _c /K _a = K _s		
		(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)
1.00	65	3.04	1.06	15.44	3.04	1.06	15.44	1.75	0.25	11.43
		±0.03	±0.02	±0.05						
0.75	65	±4.07	1.37	20.56	3.05	1.03	15.42	1.75	0.23	11.42
		0.03	±0.03	±0.05						
0.50	65	5.93	1.99	29.51	2.96	0.99	14.76	1.70	0.22	10.93
		±0.03	±0.02	±0.04						
0.25	65	11.35	4.05	59.45	2.84	1.01	14.86	1.63	0.22	11.00
		±0.04	±0.04	±0.05						
0.25	70	13.20	4.68	70.76	3.31	1.17	17.69	1.90	0.26	13.10
		±0.05	±0.04	±0.04						
0.25	75	19.49	6.11	112.31	4.87	1.53	28.08	2.80	0.33	20.80
		±0.06	±0.05	±0.07						
			ΔE (kJ mol ⁻¹)							
		(a) Thallium(III)-Acetic acid complex			46.80					
		(b) Thallium(III)-Chloroacetic acid complex			38.50					
		(c) Thallium(III)-Propionic acid complex			60.20					

An attempt was also made to obtain a direct evidence of the complex formation in these reactions by spectrophotometric method at room temperature (298 K). The results support the formation of 1 : 1 complex and the equilibrium constants for these complex formation reactions were computed by the limiting logarithmic method from the absorbance data obtained at 240 nm as 5.14, 6.29 and 6.09 mol⁻¹ respectively.

The involvement of water molecule as proton transferring agent in the rate-determining step is supported by w values (>3.3) obtained from the Bunnett plots using data of Table 3. This is also supported by Bunnett-Olsen treatment.

Experimental

The kinetic experimental details were the same as described earlier¹. The reaction was monitored iodometrically determining the concentration of unused thallium(III) in the presence of excess concentrations of hexitols and perchloric acid. Check experiments were performed to observe liberation of iodine only by Tl^{III} and not by any other reagent present in the reaction mixtures. In all the experiments, duplicate rate measurements were reproducible to within 1.5%.

The details of the epr spin trapping experiments are described elsewhere⁴.

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References

1. A. G. FADNIS and S. K. KULSHRESTHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 147; *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1982, **102**, 23; *An. Quim.*, 1986, **52**, 5; S. N. SHUKLA, R. N. KESERWANI and S. TAQI, *Oxidation Commun.*, 1984, **7**, 369; S. N. SHUKLA and R. N. KESERWANI, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1984, **133**, 319.
2. E. G. JANZEN, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1971, **4**, 31; M. J. PERKINS, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1980, **17**, 1; A. G. FADNIS, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1988, **47**, 617.
3. E. G. JANZEN and R. V. SHETTY, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1979, 3329.
4. A. G. FADNIS and T. J. KEMP, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1989, 1237; A. G. FADNIS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 273; 1990, **67**, 682; *Oxidation Commun.*, 1990, **13**, 41.
5. D. BORDERIE, D. LAVABRA, G. LEVY and J. C. MICHEAU, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1990, **67**, 459.
6. H. S. TAN and W. E. JONES, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1989, **66**, 650.
7. K. S. GUPTA and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 256; 1970, 1180.
8. J. F. LEFFLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, **20**, 1202.

